

USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS LESSONS

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Abstract: This article talks about the possibilities and advantages of using interactive methods in mathematics lessons. Methodical recommendations for organizing mathematics lessons are also presented.

Key words: school, education, interactive, teacher, student, moral education lesson, method.

Today, the great creative works in our country, the laws and decisions adopted in the field of education, the great goals set in our "National Program" encourage today's teachers to work harder and search. To have a positive result of these goals, first of all, to thoroughly teach the young generation the basics of scientific knowledge, to create in them a broad worldview and scope of thinking, to effectively organize educational and educational work on the formation of spiritual and moral qualities. is related to After all, creating a bright perspective of the country, spreading its name to the world, showing the national and cultural heritage created by great ancestors to the society, and enriching them depends on educating the young generation as a perfect person and qualified specialist.

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" adopted at the IX session of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan (August 29, 1997) and the "National Program of Personnel Training" its essence has been fully revealed. Each stage of the process of training qualified personnel should carry out certain tasks in order to effectively organize the educational process, raise it to higher levels, and bring it to the level of world education.

It is important that the employees of the continuing education system, pedagogues-teachers are aware of the nature of modern educational technologies and their ability to effectively use them in the educational process, as well as the decision of a creative approach to the organization of the educational process. . Teachers should have the skills to organize the process of lessons in the teaching of mathematics in non-traditional ways, to achieve the design of the educational process based on a perfect model, to use these projects rationally. , deep assimilation, can be a guarantee of formation of practical skills and competencies.

The educational process makes it possible to express a set of theoretical and practical knowledge on a specific topic that serves to illuminate the content of the educational material. In the content of education, it is also necessary to be able to express the concept, skills and competences that should be mastered by students. After all, the ideological perfection of the educational content is determined by the level of acquisition of certain knowledge, skills and abilities by students. The effect of this is manifested in the development of conditions that ensure the mastery of certain concepts, the formation of skills and qualifications by students.

It is the form, methods and tools of the lesson that lead to the successful provision of the educational process. Only with their help, theoretical knowledge on the subject of the study subject is transferred to the students, and this knowledge is accepted by the students. Determining the most appropriate form, method and tools for the lesson guarantees about 90% success of the educational process. The main essence of new, modern pedagogical technologies is revealed at this stage. The correct selection of educational forms, methods and tools that direct students to creative research, activity, and free thinking will make the lesson process effective, interesting, full of debates, and stimulate the emergence of creative disputes. Only in this case, the students take the initiative, and the teacher is responsible for directing their activities in a certain direction, being able to control the general activity, providing guidance in difficult situations, tasks such as giving advice and evaluating their activities remain.

One of the important requirements for the organization of modern education is to achieve high results in a short time without spending too much mental and physical effort. It is the responsibility of the teacher to deliver certain theoretical knowledge to students in a short period of time, to create skills and competencies in them for certain activities, as well as to control the activities of students, to assess the level of knowledge, skills and competencies acquired by them. requires high pedagogical skills and a new approach to the educational process. Pedagogical technologies cannot be used forcibly. On the contrary, it is appropriate to use the advanced technologies based on or used by experienced pedagogues, as well as their creative development.

Today, a lot of experience has been accumulated in the use of pedagogical technologies that increase the educational and creative activities of students and guarantee the effectiveness of the educational process, and the methods that form the basis of this experience are called interactive methods. Let's look at the

essence of some of the interactive methods used in mathematics classes and how to use them.

"Brainstorming" method. This method appears at the initial stage of the process of ensuring students' activity in the course of classes, encouraging them to think freely and freeing them from the inertia of the same thinking, collecting diverse ideas on a specific topic, and solving creative tasks. serves to learn to overcome thoughts.

"6x6x6" method. Using the "6x6x6" method, by engaging 36 students in a specific activity at the same time, it is possible to solve a certain task or problem, as well as to determine the capabilities of each member of the group, to learn their views. In the training organized on the basis of this method, 6 groups with 6 participants in each discuss the problem raised by the teacher. At the end of the specified time, the teacher will reorganize 6 groups. Each of the newly formed groups will have one representative from the previous 6 groups. The members of the newly formed group report to their teammates the conclusion presented by their group as a solution to the problem and discuss these solutions together.

"Cluster" method. The cluster method is a specific form of pedagogical, didactic strategy, which helps students create conditions for free, open thinking about optional problems, and for freely expressing personal opinions. This method requires the identification of a structure that allows thinking about the connections between different ideas. The "cluster" method is considered a form of thinking that is not directed to a specific object. Its use is carried out in connection with the principle of human brain activity. This method serves to ensure that the activity of thinking is in harmony until a specific topic is mastered by students in depth and thoroughly. The method is manifested in the form of group-based exercises and a set of ideas expressed by students. This creates an opportunity to generalize the presented ideas and find connections between them.

"Ingenious clever" method. It is important for students to have the ability to think and reflect in the thorough assimilation of existing knowledge. The "Zakovatli Zukko" method helps to form quick thinking skills in students, as well as to determine their thinking speed. The method provides a convenient opportunity for students who want to test their knowledge. They need to be able to answer the questions asked by the teacher correctly and accurately in a short period of time. According to the level of complexity of the questions, points are

assigned for the correct answer returned to each question. The method can be used in individual, group and mass work with students. "Charkhpalak" method. "Charkhpalak" technology can be used in all types of educational activities, at the beginning and end of the lesson, after the end of a section, in assessing the level of mastery of the topics covered, in repetition, reinforcement, intermediate and final controls. Lessons can be organized individually and in groups. In addition, it also excels in learning topics of various content and nature, including oral and written forms of work.

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